

MARKETING ANALYSIS OF LEISURE ACTIVITIES OF BNTU STUDENTS**Semashko A.,***Sales Manager Limited Liability Company «StroyTehDiagnostic»,
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054741>***Abstract**

The article is devoted to the marketing analysis by the CAWI-survey method, which allows to determine the degree of satisfaction with leisure activities and food outlets by students at BNTU, as well as to determine the university's opportunities in the field of leisure activities at BNTU food outlets.

Keywords: marketing analysis, leisure, students, CAWI survey, cultural and leisure activities, sample representativeness.

One of the key factors in the formation of a young person's personality is his leisure time, which has a significant impact on educational and work areas. This is due to the fact that during leisure time recreational and recovery processes occur, and the value orientations of young people are formed. In addition, the choice of leisure activities is a reflection of the culture, spiritual needs and interests of young people.

The student period is a time when a person is actively looking for himself and his lifestyle. During this period, social and moral assessments are formed and awareness of one's own strengths and weaknesses occurs, which makes it possible for targeted self-improvement and self-education. Often, students strive to critically rethink their lives and surroundings, show their independence and originality, and create their own concepts of the meaning of life. Leisure during this period is a factor in the formation and development of personality, assimilation of cultural and spiritual values [5].

The organization of leisure activities at the Belarusian National Technical University contributes to the development of the creative and intellectual potential of students, which increases their level of general culture and contributes to successful adaptation in the educational and professional spheres. In addition, thanks to a systematic and planned approach to organizing leisure activities, the university can create a comfortable and friendly atmosphere that helps bring students closer together and strengthens the collective spirit.

The purpose of the marketing research is to establish the main problems that students face during leisure time, to consider students' attitudes towards the university as a place for spending time free from classes and work, to assess the role of the university in organizing students' leisure time, to consider students' attitudes towards BNTU food outlets and assess the degree of their

satisfaction, assess the role of BNTU food outlets in organizing students' leisure time, consider and analyze students' vision of the university's capabilities in the field of organizing leisure time at BNTU food outlets.

In order to obtain accurate and reliable research results on the degree of student satisfaction with BNTU leisure activities, it is necessary to calculate the representativeness of the sample.

The general sample (the total number of objects of observation) consists of full-time students of the first stage of higher education from 1st to 5th year, who express a desire to participate in the cultural and leisure activities of BNTU. As of January 1, 2023, the number of full-time students receiving the first stage of higher education is 8,745 people.

The general sample will include 90% of students, since the remaining 10% are students who are not interested in leisure activities ($8745 \cdot 0.9 = 7,871$ people).

Using special online calculators, the sample size was calculated [1,2,3]. The required sample size based on the results of the three sites was 614 people. As of June 2, 2023, 763 people took part in the survey.

With a sample size of 763 people, a population of 7871 and a 99% confidence level, the confidence interval is 4.44%. This means that the sample is representative and the results of the marketing research can be trusted.

To conduct marketing research, the CAWI survey method was chosen. It is a method of conducting online surveys in which surveys are conducted through web pages. It uses computer technology to administer surveys, allowing respondents to receive and complete a survey online using their computer or phone. The advantages and disadvantages of the CAWI survey are presented in table 1 [6].

Table 1

Advantages and disadvantages of the CAWI survey	
Advantages of the CAWI survey	Disadvantages of the CAWI survey
Scalability: CAWI surveys can vary in scope and number of questions, which allows you to control research costs	Limited audience reach: Online surveys may miss users with limited internet access
Broad Reach: Online surveys can target a variety of target audiences, allowing for more data to be collected.	Lack of Validity: Online surveys may lack sufficient evidence, especially if high reliability is required.
Survey flexibility: CAWI surveys can be customized to specific user data to eliminate duplicate responses	Bias: Survey producers may use several technical solutions to improve responses.
Increased data accuracy: System settings ensure accurate responses, reducing the possibility of errors	Low response rate: Many users will not click on the page with the survey link
Cost-effective: CAWI surveys can be less expensive than traditional methods	

The marketing research was conducted using a CAWI survey, designed using the free multifunctional testing and training service Online Test Pad. The survey includes 54 open and closed questions.

The first block of the survey contains 6 closed-ended questions, allowing you to determine the number of students who took part in the survey from each course and understand which faculties were the most active. This block also allows you to determine what budget students have, taking into account their place of residence and form of study.

As a result of the study, 763 people were interviewed, of which 64.88% were male and 35.12% female full-time students receiving the first stage of higher education (74.97% of students - at the expense of the republican budget, 21.10% of students - at paid).

The largest proportion of respondents were 3rd year students (31.98%) and 1st year students (31.72%).

The main proportion of respondents among the faculties were students of the Faculty of Mechanical Technology (23.07%), the Faculty of Information Technology and Robotics (16.25%), the Faculty of Energy (14.42%) and the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering (13.37%).

During the analysis, it was revealed that with an increase in the course of study, students tend to stop living in a dormitory in exchange for living in a rented apartment. Presumably, this phenomenon may be due to the fact that by the 3rd-4th year, students have a desire to earn money and live independently with minimal financial support from their parents or without it at all. Therefore, they find the strength and opportunity to rent an apartment (fig. 1).

Place of residence	1 course	2 course	3 course	4 course
To the hostel	67,22%	45,36%	46,81%	37,63%
Rent an apartment	6,64%	16,39%	21,70%	27,96%
At home with parents	21,58%	26,23%	25,11%	26,88%
In my apartment	4,56%	12,02%	6,38%	7,53%
In a relatives' apartment	0,83%	0,55%	0,85%	0,00%

Fig. 1. Structure of students by place of residence depending on the course

The questions of the first part of block 2 of the questionnaire were aimed at obtaining information about the possibilities and ways of spending free time by students, in the conditions in which they currently find themselves.

Marketing research showed that 36.53% of students can devote 2 to 4 hours of their time to leisure

every day and 28% of students - from 1 to 2 hours. It is assumed that as the course of study increases, students devote less time to leisure. In order to confirm this hypothesis, it is necessary to trace the dynamics of answers to question No. 6: "How much time a day can you devote to leisure?" in the context of the first, second, third and fourth courses (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Distribution of answers to the question "How much time a day can you devote to leisure?"

There is a significant difference in the ability to devote their time to leisure activities between 1st year, 3rd year and 4th year students, since 12.43% of 3rd year students and 11.90% of 1st year students devote themselves to leisure time is from 4 to 5 hours, while only 5.21% of 4th year students can devote the same amount of time to leisure.

Based on the results obtained, it was revealed that the main reason for the discrepancy between desires and opportunities to devote more time to leisure is the fatigue of students (22.7%), lack of free time (19.90%), discrepancy between study schedules and leisure activities (18.78. %) and financial restrictions (17.28%).

According to the survey results, 34.53% of students cannot devote the desired amount of time to leisure activities due to a high academic load, while 23.60% of students are forced to combine work and study to solve financial problems and personal growth.

From figure 4 it can be seen that throughout all four courses the main reason for the lack of free time is the high workload. However, in the first two years the problem is associated primarily with a high academic load, and in the third and fourth years - with the need to combine work and study.

Thus, in the first year, 40.59% of students do not have enough free time to spend leisure time due to a high academic load, and 19.44% - due to combining work and study. In the second year, the situation is similar: 40.76% of students do not have enough free time due to a high academic load, and 22.22% due to combining work and study.

In the third year, more students combine work and study - 29.63%, and 32.07% experience difficulties due to the high academic load. In the fourth year, the situation is similar: 32.10% of students combine work and study, and 41.74% experience difficulties due to the high academic load.

Causes	1 course	2 course	3 course	4 course
High study load	40,59%	40,76%	29,96%	23,48%
I have enough free time	25,52%	21,02%	20,68%	18,26%
Insufficiently developed free time planning skills	17,99%	15,29%	8,02%	6,09%
Family responsibilities, household chores	5,86%	5,10%	9,28%	10,43%
I combine work and study	10,04%	17,83%	32,07%	41,74%

Fig. 3. Dynamics of respondents' answers to the question "What is the main reason for your lack of free time?" (depending on the course)

The most popular way of spending leisure time among students was spending time with friends; this was indicated by 81.45% of respondents. The next most popular answers were listening to music (79.26%), relaxing at home and sleeping (77.20%), walking in the

fresh air (76.05%), pursuing hobbies and hobbies (74.97%), watching movies and TV series (69.89%).

According to the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus, in 2023, the share of Internet users among people aged 14–30 years was 97.9%,

while 96.6% of young people in this age category connected to the Internet daily [7].

Moreover, the results of the CAWI survey showed that for 65.53% of students the Internet takes up most of their leisure time, and 18.74% of students believe that their leisure time is entirely related to the Internet.

The majority of students (88.07%) visit the Internet to watch videos and listen to music. Also, 78.44% of students choose the Internet as a convenient resource for finding the necessary information when preparing for a lesson, instead of independently working on searching for information in libraries. Using the Internet, 77.26% of students satisfy their need for communication.

The Internet is one of the independent types of leisure preferences of young people and serves as a means of developing their life skills and opportunities for self-expression.

The fourth block includes 13 open and closed questions that allow us to determine the most popular canteens, buffets and kiosks of BNTU among students, assess the degree of their satisfaction with BNTU food outlets, and identify the main advantages and disadvantages.

The results of the CAWI survey showed that 41.81% of students most often eat in BNTU buffets, 32.50% in canteens, the rest either take a snack with them or prefer to dine at food outlets closest to the university.

The analysis showed that 43.01% of students choose BNTU canteens and buffets for lunch and snacks because of their convenient location, which saves time on searching for places to eat. Other students (21.73%) noted that the university canteens offer low prices for food, which is suitable for students on a limited budget. Also, some students (13.83%) noted that the university canteens offer a wide range of dishes for every taste and preference, which makes food at the university varied and interesting.

According to the survey results, the main problem in the nutrition of students during the period of study at BNTU, indicated in 16.50% and 15.28% of responses, respectively, is associated with outdated design and lack of time for eating during the day. 14.06% of student responses accounted for long waits in line. Also, 11.41% of students believe that the menu is monotonous, and 13.49% of students believe that food prices are quite high (39.71% of students usually spend 5-7 Belarusian rubles on lunch, and 27.65% of students - up to 5 Belarusian rubles).

Thus, according to the results of the 4th block of the survey, 77.66% of students spend their free time in BNTU canteens and buffets to have lunch or a snack. It is worth noting that for many students, staying at food outlets is not just a way to satiate their hunger, but also a kind of leisure activity that helps them rest and relax after studying. However, many students complain

about the lack of convenient and comfortable study areas. For example, the lack of soft chairs, tables with large wooden tables and stylish interiors, which can make the experience in dining rooms or buffets more attractive and unusual.

In order to increase the attractiveness and comfort of BNTU canteens and buffets, it is necessary to pay more attention to the design and quality of seating areas, as well as make the necessary changes to meet the needs of students and make the stay at food outlets more enjoyable and attractive.

At BNTU, for holding a variety of cultural and leisure events, there is a cafe "Polytechnic", as well as banquet halls in dining room No. 2. In a cozy and comfortable atmosphere, the cafe offers services for organizing corporate evenings, anniversaries, gala lunches and dinners, buffets, children's parties, themed events, ritual events and much more.

However, as the study showed, more than 64% of the students surveyed were not aware of this possibility. This once again confirms the lack of awareness of students about the services provided by the cafe and bad advertising.

The results of the 3rd block survey showed that cultural events and sports events are the most preferred types of leisure time among students. According to the survey, 73.87% of students chose cultural events, and 73.34% of students preferred sports events.

The structure of cultural and leisure events at BNTU confirms this trend. It includes various events such as concerts, exhibitions, theater productions, sports competitions and tournaments. Most of them are held regularly and are very popular among students.

The main factors influencing the active participation of students in BNTU leisure activities are reducing stress levels and increasing life satisfaction (74.86%), maintaining physical health and shape (69.25%), and developing personal qualities (64.40%).

The majority of students (26.19%) believe that participation in BNTU leisure activities gives them a chance to spend time with friends and colleagues, as well as meet new people in an informal setting.

Also, 16.10% of students are happy to take part in leisure activities conducted by BNTU, due to encouragement from the university. Often, event organizers create a kind of loyalty program for students, offering various bonuses and privileges to those who actively participate in the life of the university.

In order to assess the degree of satisfaction with leisure activities conducted by the Belarusian National Technical University (BNTU), it is necessary to determine the significant shortcomings of the cultural and leisure activities of the university among interested students and actively participating in various events. The respondents' answers are presented in figure 4.

Fig. 4. Structure of respondents' answers to the question "Disadvantages of cultural and leisure activities of the university"

Based on the survey results, we can conclude that it is necessary to take into account the schedule of academic classes when planning leisure activities, since more than a third of the students surveyed (30.72%) indicated that the schedule of cultural and leisure activities is inconvenient for them due to the intersection with the schedule steam.

Also, 19.92% of students believe that the organizers do not sufficiently inform students about upcoming events. This fact indicates the need for more active advertising and dissemination of information about cultural and leisure events that are organized for students. It is worth paying more attention to the use of various communication channels, such as social networks, emails, notifications on websites, etc. This approach will not only increase the level of awareness of students, but also attract a larger number of participants to events, which, in turn, contributes to the development of cultural life at BNTU and the creation of a more friendly atmosphere among students.

From a survey of BNTU students, it became known that 14.34% of respondents believe that the university does not have convenient and comfortable areas for leisure activities. Since "the opportunity to rest and relax" and "increasing cultural potential" are considered the most important factors when choosing leisure

activities for students, to improve the situation, special attention should be paid to creating such areas and offering students various options for relaxation and recreation.

As mentioned earlier, in BNTU for holding a variety of cultural and leisure events, there is a cafe "Polytechnic", as well as banquet halls of dining room No. 2, however, these establishments are not popular, since according to the survey results, in addition to insufficient awareness of students about the events held at BNTU, Most students felt that BNTU food outlets had an outdated design and a monotonous menu. In this regard, students can be offered several options for leisure activities, taking into account the elimination of all identified shortcomings in the organization of leisure activities and the organization of the work of BNTU food outlets.

The most preferred leisure activities in the banquet hall of dining room №2 were watching a movie (28.80%) and holding parties and discos (12.86%). The results of this question are presented in figure 5.

The survey results showed that more than half of the students (62.52%) are willing to spend up to 15 rubles on leisure activities in the BNTU banquet hall, only 2.88% are willing to spend more than 50 rubles.

Fig. 5. Desired leisure activities among students at the BNTU banquet hall

Based on the results of a CAWI survey among BNTU students, the following leisure services were formed, held in the banquet hall of BNTU dining room №2: cinema room, theme parties, holidays, discos, board games, master classes in various areas, trainings, meetings, lectures, networking, billiards, the game “Mafia”, holding intellectual games [4].

A possible version of the interior of a banquet hall for leisure events is presented in Figure 6. Visualization of the interior was carried out using a professional tool for creating design projects - Planoplan.

Fig. 6. Visualization of the interior of a banquet hall for organizing leisure activities

When designing the interior, attention was first paid to the most necessary equipment, such as a projector, projection screen, upholstered furniture and audio system. Based on the area of the banquet hall, the room was arranged in such a way that students could comfortably spend their leisure time in a cozy atmosphere.

Thus, the organization of cultural and leisure activities, as well as its improvement, can play an im-

portant role in the professional development and formation of students’ potential. Such activities have an impact on the emotional sphere of the individual, creating conditions for the active participation of students in various events aimed at the personal and professional development of students, the formation of an active professional position of students as the basis for their future professional achievements.

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